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Development of air-jet spun polymeric membranes for wound healing applications

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Introduction: Delayed wound healing is a major healthcare challenge which affects the quality of life and results in a financial burden to the patient as well as the public healthcare system. The advancement of nanotechnology has enabled the development of cost-effective wound-coverage materials such as nanofibrous matrices having large porosity, high-surface-to-volume ratios, and extracellular matrix mimetic features. Electrospinning offers a distinct advantage because it has a wide range and the ability to integrate inorganic components on nanoscale, making it ideal for a variety of applications in wound healing and tissue engineering (1). The slow processing rate of fiber, however, impedes the electrospinning process and it requires polymer solution with sufficient conductivity to form a polymer jet. Air-jetbased spinning is a low-cost option for generating polymeric fiber-based membranes quickly and uniformly on a variety of substrates (2). Polycaprolactone (PCL) (1) and Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) (2) are two biodegradable polymers used for various biomedical applications. In this work, we used air jet spinning to fabricate PCL and Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) based polymeric membranes as highly interconnected porous structures for wound healing applications.

Methods: PHBV/PCL blend polymer solution was used for fabricating PHBV/PCL fiber mats by air-jet spinning. Different ratios of the PHBV/PCL were prepared to find out the optimum combination which can provide enough strength and desirable biological properties. The developed membranes were characterized by techniques such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis. Thermal analysis was carried out using DSC and TGA. Uniaxial tensile mechanical testing was carried out to check the effect of blending of polymers on the tensile strength of the fibers. *In vitro* cell culture studies using 3T3 fibroblasts were performed to understand the effect of PHBV/PCL membranes on cell adhesion and proliferation.

Results & Discussions: SEM data shows that the fiber diameters varied in the sub-micrometer scale. The crystallinity of the fibers increased as the PCL content increased, according to the XRD data. DSC results showed that the two polymers exist in the composite as relatively immiscible components. The tensile strength was observed to increase with the increasing concentration of PCL. The cell adhesion study using 3T3 cells showed that the cells showed better fiber attachment with increasing PHBV content.

Conclusions: Based on our preliminary studies, it can reasonably be concluded that PHBV/PCL blends having 1:1 ratio of each polymer show the improvement in mechanical and cell adhesion properties. Therefore, air-jet spun PHBV/PCL membranes can be used for developing wound healing patches and tissue engineering scaffolds.

Key words: *Air-jet spinning, Composite fibers, Wound healing*

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